

Strategy to Prevent Corruption in the Procurement of Defence Equipment in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study formulates a strategy to prevent corruption in the procurement of the of Defence Equipment in Indonesia. The method used is a literature study which in collecting information and data uses the help of various kinds of materials in the library such as documents, books, magazines, historical stories, etc. The results of this study indicate that the Strategy for Preventing Corruption in the Procurement of Alutsista within the Ministry of Defense and the TNI includes strengthening the legal framework, evaluating bids, delegating authority, auditing and independent audits. This strategy must also be supported by Increasing the Integrity and Ethics of Organizers, Consolidating and Accelerating State Bureaucratic Reform, Strengthening the Anti-Corruption Culture of the Community, Firm, Consistent, and Integrated Law Enforcement.

KEYWORDS - Strategy, Procurement, Equipment, Corruption, Defence

I. INTRODUCTION

Based on the 2019 Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) Annual Report, in the period 2004 to 2019 corruption cases handled by the KPK with the mode of procurement of goods and services amounted to 206 cases out of a total of 1032 cases handled. The mode of procurement of goods and services is the second highest under the case with the mode of bribery which amounted to 683 cases. This is in line with what was conveyed by Kaufmann in Richo (2015) who stated that the procurement of goods/services (PBJ) is a government activity that is considered the most vulnerable to corruption, and this happens anywhere in the world.

Indonesia is the 15th largest country in the world with a total land area of 1,919,440 km and an area of ocean 3.2 million km². Indonesia is the largest archipelagic country in the world which has 17,508 islands. To create defense and security for all its people, the Government of Indonesia in 2021 will allocate a budget in the defense sector of Rp 136.9 trillion, which is the second largest budget after the infrastructure development budget. Of the total budget of Rp 9.3 trillion for the procurement of defense equipment.

A large enough budget for the procurement of defense equipment must of course be used appropriately and free from corruption. This is because according to the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia on Anti-Corruption Education said that the existence of corruption in the defense and security sector will have an impact on three things, namely Weak Alutsista and Human Resources, Weak national boundaries and strengthening of violence in society.

One of the cases that became a mega-corruption scandal in the field of defense equipment procurement in Indonesia was the procurement case Backbone Coastal Surveillance System(BCSS) at the Maritime Security Agency (Bakamla). In his indictment at the Central Jakarta Corruption Court, it was stated that the suspects had committed or participated in committing acts, namely unlawfully enriching themselves and others that could harm state finances or the state economy in the amount of Rp. 63,829.0008.006.92.

In the study of defense science, corruption prevention strategies are included in one form of non-military defense. According to Guntur (2021), non-military defense is a national defense force that is built in the context of national development to achieve national prosperity and is ready to face non-military threats. So that corruption in the defense sector is not only considered an extraordinary crime but also a threat to national defense.

Based on this background, the researchers tried to develop a Corruption Prevention Strategy for the procurement of defense equipment in Indonesia. With the hope of strategyng formulated later can be used by stakeholders in compiling and implementing the procurement of defense equipment in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Strategy

According to Tjiptono (2008), the term strategy comes from the Greek strategy (stratos = military and ag = lead), which means the art or science of becoming a general. Strategy can be interpreted as a plan for the distribution and use of military and material forces in certain areas to achieve certain goals of action.

Meanwhile, according to David (2004), strategy is a unified, broad and integrated plan that links the company's strategic advantages with environmental challenges, designed to ensure that the main objectives of the company can be achieved through proper implementation by the organization.

Strategy is formulated as setting a goal and allocating the resources most likely to result in an effective fit. Strategic capability in the organization greatly influences the implementation of strategy and skills are not only used for strategy development, but also for strategy implementation as part of strategic management (Armstrong, 1996).

In this study, the strategy formulation will be discussed as mentioned by General (Ret) Andrew J. Good Paster in AcmadBastari et al (2018), has three elements, namely ends, means, and ways. These three elements must be contained in carrying out a strategy.

2.2. Corruption

According to Robert Klitgaardet. al (2002) corruption is an action in the form of:

1. Collecting money for services that are supposed to be provided.
2. Using authority to achieve illegitimate goals.
3. Not carrying out tasks due to negligence or forgetfulness.

Meanwhile, according to the Association of Certified Fraud Examinations (ACFE) in Amrizal (2004) corruption is divided into conflicts of interest, bribery, illegal gratuity, and economic extortion.

However, the corruption referred to in this research is corruption according to Law Number 28 of 1999 concerning the Implementation of a State that is Clean and Free from Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism and the researcher uses a different definition of corruption according to Law Number 28 of 1999 concerning State Administration which is Clean and Free from Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism as well as Law Number 31 of 1999 which has been amended by Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning the eradication of corruption.

From the two regulations, it can be seen that what is included in the criminal act of corruption in Indonesia is different from the corruption presented by Robert Klitgaard and ACFE. The basic difference is that in Indonesia, an act can only be said to be a criminal act of corruption if the action is detrimental to the state's financial losses or the state's economy.

2.3. Corruption Prevention Strategy

The current government continues to strive to combat corruption in Indonesia. One form of the government's seriousness is the involvement of Indonesia in United Nations Convention Against Corruption 2003 (United Nations Convention Against Corruption, 2003), which was later ratified in Law Number 7 of 2006.

As a consequence of the ratification of the law, the Government issued Presidential Regulation Number 55 of 2012 (Perpres 55 of 2012) concerning the National Strategy for Corruption Prevention and Eradication of Corruption in the Long Term of 2012-2025 and the Medium Term of 2012-2014 (Stranas KDP). Then the Presidential Regulation was revoked and updated with Presidential Regulation Number 54 of 2018 concerning the National Strategy for Corruption Prevention which contains focus and targets in accordance with the needs of preventing corruption so that corruption prevention can be carried out in a more focused, measurable, and direct manner in order to create a just, prosperous society. , and prosper.

The National Strategy for Corruption Prevention, hereinafter referred to as Stranas PK, is a national policy direction that contains the focus and targets for preventing corruption which is used as a reference for ministries, institutions, local governments and other stakeholders in carrying out corruption prevention actions in Indonesia. Corruption Prevention Action, hereinafter referred to as PK Action, is the elaboration of the focus and targets of the National Strategy for PKing in the form of programs and activities.

Some experts provide a broader definition, namely not only preventing corruption but also preventing fraud. As stated in (COSO; 1992:13), fraud prevention in general is an activity carried out in terms of establishing policies, systems and procedures that help ensure that the necessary actions have been taken by the board of commissioners, management, and other personnel within the company to be able to provide assurance. Adequate in achieving organizational goals, namely: Effectiveness and efficiency of operations, reliability of financial reports, and compliance with applicable laws and regulations.

According to Tuanakotta (2007:162), fraud prevention can be done by activating internal controls. Active internal control is usually the most widely applied form of internal control. It is like fences that prevent thieves from entering people's yards. Like a fence, however strong, it can still be penetrated by fraudsters who are clever and have the guts to do it.

And according to Pope (2007) in Hermiyeti (2009), prevention of fraud in terms of procurement of public goods, among others:

1. Strengthen the legal framework.

2. Transparent procedure
3. Open tender document
4. Offer evaluation
5. Delegate authority
6. Independent inspection and audit

In this study, how to prevent corruption, which will be discussed in the strategy for preventing corruption in the procurement of defense equipment in Indonesia, uses indicators or recommendations in preventing fraud as stated by Pope (2007).

2.4. Procurement of defense equipment in Indonesia

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the procurement of goods and services means an offer to submit a price and buy up work for the provision of goods/services. Based on Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 12 of 2021 (Perpres 12 of 2021) concerning Amendments to Presidential Regulation Number 16 of 2018 concerning Procurement of Government Goods and Services, it is stated that Government Procurement of Goods/Services, hereinafter referred to as Procurement of Goods/Services is an activity of Procurement of Goods/Services by the Ministry/Agency/Regional Apparatus financed, by the APBN/APBD whose process starts from the identification of needs, until the handover of the results of the work.

With the revocation of the Regulation of the Minister of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia Number 17 of 2014 concerning the Implementation of Procurement of Main Weapon System Equipment within the Ministry of Defense and the Indonesian National Army. So the rules governing the Procurement of Alutsista within the Indonesian Armed Forces and the Indonesian Ministry of Defense are currently regulated in the Minister of Defense Regulation number 16 of 2019 concerning the Implementation of the Procurement of Defense and Security Equipment Tools within the Ministry of Defense and the Indonesian National Armed Forces (Permenhan 16 of 2019).

In this regulation, Alutsista is included in the category of Defense and Security Equipment Tools (Apalhankam). In theory, the procurement of defense equipment is also included in the defense acquisition. Where do you think According to ZainalAbidin S (2020), defense acquisition is a series of complex procurement processes for defense equipment systems based on differences in capabilities and opportunities for technological improvement. He also explained that procurement in defense acquisitions can be carried out in 4 ways, namely domestic production, collaboration, offset and imports.

Figure 1

Source :ZainalAbidin S, 2020, Textbook of Procurement of Defense Equipment and Logistics.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this study, we use the type/approach of research in the form of Library Research. According to Mandalis (1999) in Mirzaqon&Purwoko (2018), literature study is a study that is used to collect information and data with the help of various materials in the library such as documents, books, magazines, historical stories, etc.

Literature study also means data collection techniques by reviewing books, literature, notes, and various reports related to the problem to be solved (Nazir: 1988). Meanwhile, according to other experts, literature study is a theoretical study, references and other scientific literature related to culture, values and norms that develop in the social situation under study (Sugiyono: 2012).

The strategic approach used in this research is the strategy theory approach presented by Gen. US Army (Ret) Andrew J. Good Paster where he stated that "Strategy covers what we should do (ends), how we should do it (ways), and what we should do it with (means)". (Nelson, 2016, pp. 243-244).

IV. RESULTS OR DISCUSSION

In line with Andrew J. Good Paster according to SalehaMufida, et al (2020) strategy is a decision-making process on the main elements of a strategy, namely:includes Ends (goals, objects, targets), Ways (ways of action, concepts, methods) and Means (means, strengths, resources, potentials). Thus the formulation of the strategy must contain these three elements and must be balanced.

4.1. Ends (goal, object, target)

In Presidential Decree 12 of 2021 it is explained that the objectives of the Procurement of Goods and Services are:

- a. Reducing the right goods/services from every money spent, measured from aspects of quality, quantity, time, cost, location, and provider.
- b. Increase the use of domestic products.
- c. Increase the participation of Micro, Small Business, and Cooperatives.
- d. Increasing the role of national business actors.
- e. Support the implementation of research and utilization of research goods/services.
- f. Increase the participation of the reactive industry.
- g. Realizing economic equality and providing expansion of business opportunities.
- h. Improving Sustainable Procurement.

Procurement is one of the four elements of development in the Minimum Essential Force (MEF) where according to Ervita (2020), the MEF program aims to develop and modernize defense forces to be more

effective in carrying out military tasks and also tasks in peace missions. The MEF has been launched by the Government since 2007, then the MEF policy has been implemented since 2009 which is divided into three phases, namely the first phase of 2010-2014, the second phase of 2015-2019, and the third phase of 2020-2024. The MEF is targeted at 100 percent at the end of the MEF phase III, namely at the end of 2024. The MEF achievement in both MEF I and MEF II is still below the target that has been set. In October 2019, MEF achievement only reached 63.19 percent of the MEF phase II target of 75.54 percent.

Figure 2

Achievements of the Physical Aspects of the MEF Defence Equipment Sector until October 7, 2019

Source: Directorate General of Defense, Ministry of Defense (2019) quoted from Ervita (2020)

Based on these data, it can be seen that it is still necessary to increase the procurement of defense equipment to achieve the 100% MEF target in 2024. With the achievement of the MEF, it is hoped that the implementation of national defense is to maintain state sovereignty, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from threats and disturbances. towards the integrity of the nation and state as referred to in Article 1 paragraph 1 of Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense can be achieved.

From the discussion, it can be seen that the strategy to prevent corruption in the procurement of defense equipment in Indonesia has the main goal of strengthening the implementation of national defense through the achievement of the MEF targets that have been set. This is because the MEF target that has been set since 2019 is still being pursued by the Indonesian Ministry of Defense as explained in the 2021 Ministry/Agency Work Plan and Budget Set.

4.2. Ways (way of action, concept, method)

According to Purnomo (2014), the Ministry of Defense's policy in procuring armaments is to prioritize domestic production as much as possible. If it is not possible and must be carried out from abroad, efforts will be made to implement it on a G to G basis, joint production, transfer of technology, counter trade, offset, guarantee of freedom of use and guarantee of spare parts.

In general, the procurement process for the TNI Alutsista has been regulated in the Minister of Defense Regulation number 16 of 2019 concerning the Implementation of the Procurement of Defense and Security Equipment Tools within the Ministry of Defense and the Indonesian National Army. However, in this study, the researchers tried to formulate a strategy for preventing corruption in the procurement of defense equipment by describing 6 things according to Pope (2007), namely: strengthening the legal framework, transparent procedures, opening tender documents, evaluating bids, delegating authority, independent inspection and audit.

4.2.1. Strengthening the legal framework

According to Hermiyeti (2009), in Indonesia there is a reference to what is called a criminal act of corruption, namely Law Number 31 of 1999 which has been amended by Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning the eradication of criminal acts of corruption. This is in line with what was conveyed by Piping, et al (2014) who stated that in corruption cases involving government agencies or companies, the regulation that becomes a reference for eradicating corruption in Indonesia is Law Number 31 of 1999 in conjunction with Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning Eradication of corruption. Corruption Act. The articles that are often used are articles 2 and 3.

According to Piping et al (2014), to conclude whether an act includes corruption according to Article 2, it must meet the following elements:

- a. Each person
- b. Enrich yourself, others or a corporation
- c. By way of against the law
- d. Can harm state finances or the country's economy

Meanwhile, to conclude whether an act includes corruption according to Article 3, it must meet the following elements:

- a. Each person
- b. With the aim of benefiting oneself, another person or a corporation
- c. Abusing authority, opportunity or means
- d. There is a position or position
- e. Can harm state finances or the country's economy

So that the legal framework that regulates related to the procurement of defense equipment should be separated from the elements of corruption that exist in the two articles. These elements appear in Minister of Defense 16 of 2019 which is located in Article 4 (Principles of Procurement) and Article 5 (Procurement Ethics).

However, there are still shortcomings in the regulation because it does not include strict sanctions for parties who commit criminal acts of corruption as stated in Law Number 31 of 1999 which has been amended by Law Number 20 of 2001 concerning the eradication of criminal acts. corruption. For example in Article 71 paragraph 4 of the Minister of Defense 16 of 2019 it is stated that providers who are proven to have committed acts or acts of corruption will be given several sanctions including:

- a. Sanctions are waived in elections.

- b. Guarantee disbursement sanction.
- c. Blacklist Sanctions.
- d. Compensation sanctions.
- e. Fines.

Should if proven to have committed a criminal act of corruption the sanction given is a criminal sanction as stated in the Law Number 31 of 1999 which has been amended by Law Number 20 of 2001. The sanctions include:

- a. Sentenced to imprisonment for life or imprisonment for a minimum of 4 (four) years and a maximum of 20 (twenty).
- b. A fine of at least Rp. 200,000,000.00 (two hundred million rupiah) and a maximum of Rp. 1.000.000.000,00 (one billion rupiah).
- c. Death penalty under certain circumstances

A strong legal framework will encourage the prevention of corruption in the procurement of defense equipment in Indonesia. By including strict sanctions in regulations related to procurement, it will further prevent corruption in these activities. Existing regulations should no longer implicitly regulate the perpetrators of acts of corruption. The existing legal framework should strictly regulate the criminal acts of corruption committed and the existing sanctions are not only administrative in nature but also criminal as regulated in Law Number 31 of 1999 which has been amended by Law Number 20 of 2001.

4.2.2. Transparent procedure

According to Purnomo (2014), the defense equipment procurement process follows a long chain starting from the users, namely their respective forces (spec-tec), TNI Headquarters (opsreq), the Ministry of Defense (Administration and Contracts), the Ministry of Finance (as the cornerstone of for submissions to the DPR RI), DPR RI (creating an asterisk), back to the Ministry of Finance (Loan Agreement), then Bank Indonesia (LC).

This long process is expected to run transparently at every stage. According to Hermiyeti (2009), apart from the legal framework, the next defense against fraud is open and transparent procedures and practices to carry out the procurement process itself. No one has yet found a better way to fight fraud in procurement than a supplier or contractor selection procedure based on fair competition. And to support the creation of this, the following elements can be considered from each procedure carried out:

- a. Outline clearly and impartially what to buy.
- b. Announce the opportunity to offer goods.
- c. Develop criteria for making decisions at the time of selection.
- d. Accept offers from responsible suppliers.
- e. Compare bids and determine the best bid, according to predefined rules for selection.

f. Award the contract to the winning bidder without requiring him to lower the price or make any other

changes to his winning bid.

However, these elements are difficult to fulfill in the procurement of defense equipment. This is due to the nature of the security sector, especially military defense which is considered a sensitive strategic sector so that it is closed and exclusive. It is as stated by RonMatthews in his article entitled *Defense and the economy* an introduction sees that for a long time the state has treated the security sector, especially military defense as an exclusive and closed strategic domain. Meet the needs of the national military self-reliance. In the US, for example, a Buy America regulation has been made that protects the national defense industry of the European Union, Russia, including the Soviet Union, and developing countries such as China, India, Pakistan, Malaysia and Singapore have similar policies.

This also happened in Indonesia, such as during a budget discussion meeting related to the modernization of defense equipment which was carried out by the Ministry of Defense with Commission I of the Indonesian House of Representatives on Wednesday, June 2, 2021, which took place behind closed doors. After obtaining approval from the forum, the Chairperson of Commission I of the DPR-RI MeutyaHafid decided to hold the meeting held behind closed doors. He said at the beginning of the meeting, "We first agreed on the nature of the meeting. We from the leadership have consulted for a meeting related to the budget, which will discuss, among others, the defense equipment that is planned to be purchased. As usual, we will open the meeting in a closed manner,".

Based on the description and discussion, it can be seen that the element of transparent procedures cannot be carried out in the strategy of preventing corruption in the procurement of defense equipment because it is closed and exclusive due to its very strategic position for national defense and security.

4.2.3. Open tender document

Opening the tender document is actually a continuation of the previous element, namely the transparent procedure. According to Hermiyeti (2009), the key to realizing transparency and impartiality is that the buyer opens the tender document at the time and place that has been determined, in front of all bidders or their representatives who wish to attend. The practice of disclosing tender documents publicly, so that everyone can see who made bids and at what price, can reduce the risk that confidential tenders are leaked to other participants, ignored, altered or manipulated.

This element also cannot be implemented in the strategy to prevent corruption in the procurement of defense equipment because it is considered to cause other parties who are not interested in knowing the defense and security forces that will be built with the procurement of defense equipment.

This element also cannot be fulfilled because the existing defense equipment procurement method in Indonesia only consists of three methods as stated in article 34 paragraph 2 Minister of Defense 16 of 2019, namely:

- a. Direct appointment.
- b. Special Election.
- c. Direct Purchase.

The three methods do not allow the open disclosure of tender documents to other parties.

4.2.4. Offer evaluation

Bid evaluation is the key to controlling the procurement of defense equipment, this is because the previous two elements cannot be implemented in the procurement of defense equipment. According to Hermiyeti (2009), bid evaluation is the most difficult step in the procurement process to be carried out correctly and fairly. At the same time this step is one of the easiest to manipulate if an official wants to direct the winning decision to a particular supplier. Assessors may reject unwanted offers on the grounds sought, usually involving a breach of procedure – a mark has been deleted, a page has not been initialed – or on the grounds of deviation from the specifications, which their demands are substantial. After the offer is checked, if nothing stands in the way,

Parties who evaluate bids must not only be competent, they must also have high integrity, in general they must handle integrity pacts in the procurement of goods and services carried out. So important is this process that the next two stages or strategies namely delegation of authority and independent audit will focus on this stage.

4.2.5. Bestow authority

Delegation of authority is the next strategy in preventing corruption in the procurement of defense equipment. Delegation of authority will lead to more parties controlling each other in the implementation of defense equipment procurement.

An example of the delegation of authority is in the process of determining the winner. Where the Minister of Defense 16 of 2019, the authority to determine the winner is divided into three, namely:

- a. Determination and notification of winners as referred to in Article 44 letter b, procurement with a ceiling above Rp. 100,000,000.00 (one hundred billion rupiah) for procurement originating from centralized budget funds (PLN/PDN) and development of defense industry technology, determination of winners by the Minister as PA after going through the evaluation of the Procurement Evaluation Team.
- b. Procurement with a ceiling above Rp100,000,000,000.00 (one hundred billion rupiah) for procurement originating from Foreign Exchange Budget funds and pure rupiah, the determination of the winner by KPA in accordance with the delegation of authority through the budget execution list.
- c. Determination of the winner of the Alpalhankam Procurement with a maximum value of Rp. 100,000,000.00 (one hundred billion rupiah) for procurement originating from the Foreign Exchange Budget and pure rupiah, the determination of the winner by the Election Working Group.

According to Hermiyeti (2009), the reasons for delegating authority are quite convincing: lower officials have the authority to assess and approve small purchases, while higher officials have the authority to review appraisals by subordinates and approve large contracts. The greater the value of the contract, the higher the rank of the official authorized to make the decision to approve it or not.

4.2.6. Inspection and independent audit

Inspection or supervision is absolutely necessary to prevent corruption in the procurement of defense equipment. But on the other hand, the supervision and inspection carried out must also be effective and efficient so as not to hinder the implementation of the defense equipment procurement.

In Indonesia, supervision of the procurement of defense equipment within the Ministry of Defense and the TNI according to Minister of Defense 16 of 2019 is carried out under the control of the Inspectorate General of the Indonesian Ministry of Defense. On the one hand, supervision by the internal inspectorate is often considered less independent, but in the defense sector it is important to maintain secrecy so that all types of supervision should be under the control of the Inspectorate General of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Indonesia. However, in the supervision process, the element of confidentiality must not eliminate the three main elements in supervision, namely effectiveness, efficiency and economy.

4.3. Means (means, strengths, resources, potential).

According to Hanri and Guntur (2021), a process of activities to be carried out will not be able to achieve the expected results according to the plan, if the facilities and resources are not available. For this reason, the infrastructure and resources owned must be optimized as much as possible.

And according to Waluyo. (2014). To optimize the eradication of corruption, a holistic strategy is needed, namely:

4.3.1. Improving the Integrity and Ethics of State Administrators.

Weak integrity and ethics of state administrators or apparatus are the main causes of irregularities and abuse of authority or power. The state apparatus is the main factor in the success of the government in realizing good governance, clean, and free of corruption, collusion, nepotism (KKN). Without an apparatus with integrity and ethics, it is impossible for the government's work program to run properly. For this reason, one of the main aspects of the bureaucratic reform program is the reform of the human resources (HR) aspect, because this aspect will later implement or drive all bureaucratic reform programs.

4.3.2. Consolidation and Acceleration of Bureaucratic Reform.

Bureaucratic reform is an effort to rearrange the government bureaucracy in order to be able to provide excellent service to the community. Bureaucratic reform initially covered 3 (three) main aspects, namely: Institutional (organization); Management (business process); and human resources (apparatus).

a. Institutional Aspect

Reforms in the institutional sector are needed to reorganize the organizational structure in order to form an organization that has the right function and size (right sizing) so as to create a modern organization that is able to support the implementation of tasks and functions in an effective, efficient, transparent, and accountable manner and prioritize services to the community.

b. Management Aspect

Reforms in the field of governance are needed so that in every implementation of tasks and functions, both technical, juridical and administrative, have clear guidelines so that the results can be clearly measured.

Management reform is carried out by establishing clear, orderly, non-overlapping systems, processes and work procedures (SOPs), in accordance with the principles of good governance.

c. Aspects of Human Resources (HR)

Reforms in the field of HR include 3 (three) things, namely: changes in mindset (mindset), changes in work culture (culture set), and changes in behavior (behavior).

d. Strengthening Society's Anti-Corruption Culture.

Efforts to realize good governance, clean, and free from KKN in essence cannot only be carried out by state apparatus or government agencies. Because in essence there are 3 (three) stakeholders in good, clean, and free governance, namely: the state, the private sector, and the community. State or government, the concept of government is basically a state activity, but further than that it also involves the private sector and community institutions; private sector, private sector actors include private companies that are active in interactions in the market system, such as: trade processing industry, banking, and cooperatives, including informal sector activities; and society, in the context of the state, community groups are basically in the middle or between the government and individuals,

4.3.3. Firm, Consistent, and Integrated Law Enforcement.

Consistent and integrated law enforcement is very important for the realization of the pillars of justice and legal certainty. The pillars of justice and legal certainty are the main foundations of the democratization process. Democratization is one of the principles of good governance, because democratization opens up space for the public to participate in the administration of the state. In addition, legal certainty is also very necessary for businesses in investing in a country. Because without legal certainty, the risk of doing business cannot be predicted so that it can reduce the investment climate. The small number of investments will reduce new jobs for the community, so that there will be a lot of unemployment which has the potential to pose a threat and disturbance to security.

Furthermore, consistent and integrated law enforcement will also bring benefits to the community, namely the emergence of a deterrent effect, so that it can prevent someone who wants to commit corruption. Another benefit is the growth of public trust in law enforcement efforts and law enforcement officials, so that public support for law enforcement agencies will be strengthened. On the other hand, if there is inconsistency and incoherence in law enforcement, the public will judge that in the process of law enforcement there is a tug of war of interest, so that trust in law enforcement will weaken. The implication is that this will weaken the legal culture and compliance with the law by the community.

V. CONCLUSION

From the results of the discussion in the previous section, it can be concluded as follows:

- a. Based on the data on the Achievement of Physical Aspects of the MEF Alutsista Sector until October 7, 2019 it can be seen that it is still necessary to increase the procurement of defense equipment to achieve the 100% MEF target in 2024. With the achievement of the MEF, it is hoped that the implementation of state defense is to maintain the sovereignty of the country, the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Indonesia, and the safety of the entire nation from threats and disturbances to the

integrity of the nation and state as referred to in Article 1 paragraph 1 of Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense can be achieved.

- b. The achievement of the procurement of defense equipment as targeted in the MEF can be optimized with the Corruption Prevention Strategy in the Procurement of Alutsista within the Ministry of Defense and the TNI. Where in this strategy there must be three things, namely Ends (goals, goals, objects, targets), Ways (ways of acting, concepts, methods) and Means (means, strengths, resources, potential) that are good and right.
- c. Ends The main (target, objective, object, target) of the Strategy for Prevention of Corruption in the Procurement of Alutsista within the Ministry of Defense and the TNI is to achieve the MEF which is targeted to be achieved 100% by 2024.
- d. Ways (how to act, concepts, methods) of the Strategy to Prevent Corruption in the Procurement of Alutsista within the Ministry of Defense and the TNI include strengthening the legal framework, evaluating bids, delegating authority, independent audits and inspections.
- e. Means (means, strengths, resources, potential) of the Strategy for Prevention of Corruption in the Procurement of Alutsista within the Ministry of Defense and the TNI include Improving the Integrity and Ethics of Operators, Consolidating and Accelerating State Bureaucratic Reforms, Strengthening Anti-Corruption Culture in the Community, Firm and Consistent Law Enforcement , and Integrated

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